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**Response of proinflammatory and antiinflammatory cytokines in calves
with subclinical bovine viral diarrhoea challenged with bovine
herpesvirus-1**

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26

Abstract

27 The aim of this work was to investigate the profile of cytokines implicated in the
28 inflammatory and immune response of calves experimentally infected with a non-
29 cytopathic strain of bovine viral diarrhea virus (BVDV) genotype-1 and challenged with
30 bovine herpesvirus 1.1 (BHV-1.1) in comparison with healthy animals challenged only
31 with BHV-1.1, for evaluating the mechanisms used by BVDV to enhance the
32 susceptibility to a secondary infection. The inflammatory and immune response was
33 measured by serum concentrations of cytokines (IL-1 β , TNF α , IFN γ , IL-12, IL-4 and IL-
34 10), acute phase proteins (haptoglobin, serum amyloid A and fibrinogen) and BVDV and
35 BHV-1.1 specific antibodies. The BVDV-infected calves displayed impaired cytokine
36 profiles following BHV-1 infection, leading to an exacerbation of the inflammatory
37 response and to the development of more intense clinical symptoms and lesions than
38 those observed in healthy animals as a response to a secondary infection. BVDV does not
39 appear to impair the development of a clear Th1 immune response that was observed in
40 both groups of BHV-1-inoculated calves. However, the BVDV-infected calves showed
41 an alteration in the kinetics and magnitude of IFN γ and IL-12 production, two cytokines
42 involved in the cytotoxic mechanisms responsible for limiting the spread of pathogens
43 giving rise to secondary infections, thus facilitating the dissemination of BHV-1.1.

44

45 **Keywords:** bovine viral diarrhea virus; bovine herpesvirus type 1; immune
46 response; cytokines; acute phase proteins; ELISA.

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48

49

Abbreviations

50	BVDV	bovine viral diarrhea virus
51	cp	cytopathogenic
52	npc	non-cytopathogenic
53	DCs	dendritic cells
54	APR	acute phase response
55	APPs	acute phase proteins
56	Hp	haptoglobin
57	SAA	serum amyloid A
58	BVD	Bovine Viral Diarrhea
59	BHV-1	bovine herpesvirus-1
60	BHV1 group	group of animals inoculated only with BHV-1
61	BVDV/BHV1 group	group of animals inoculated with BVDV and BHV-1
62	TCID ₅₀	tissue culture infective dose 50%
63	dpi	days post-inoculation
64	hpi	hours post-inoculation
65	RNA	ribonucleic acid
66	RT-PCR	reverse transcription-polymerase chain reaction
67	Ct	cycle threshold
68	DNA	deoxyribonucleic acid
69	Rt	room temperature
70	VN	virus neutralization
71	MDBK	Madin Darby Bovine Kidney cells

72

Introduction

73 Bovine viral diarrhea virus (BVDV) is an endemic ruminant pestivirus in
74 populations worldwide. Two genotypes, BVDV1 and BVDV2, are recognized as distinct
75 species within this genus, being classified in cytopathogenic (cp) and non-cytopathogenic
76 (ncp) based on their activity on cultured epithelial cells (Ridpath et al., 1994; Heinz et al.,
77 2000; Fulton et al., 2003). Although acute BVDV infections are often asymptomatic or
78 produce only mild clinical symptoms, there is evidence that they induce lymphopenia and
79 a range of effects on the immune response which allow the appearance of secondary
80 infections (Peterhans et al., 2003; Liebler-Tenorio et al., 2004; Pedrera et al., 2009b).
81 BVDV infects a wide variety of cell types but has a predilection for cells of the immune
82 system as monocytes/macrophages (m-M ϕ s), dendritic cells (DCs) and lymphocyte
83 populations (Glew et al., 2003; Liebler-Tenorio et al., 2003). The consequences of
84 infection include the death of these cells populations as an extreme event, or more subtle
85 effects on cytokine expression and synthesis of co-stimulatory molecules (Rescigno and
86 Borrow, 2001; Schneider-Schaulies et al., 2002). Thus, the changes in the profile of
87 cytokines, produced by immune or non-immune cells, could affect to both innate and
88 specific immunity (Nobiron et al., 2001).

89 Proinflammatory cytokines as IL-1 and TNF α are of great importance in the
90 innate immune response (Biron and Sen, 2001), causing leukocyte chemoattraction,
91 phagocyte stimulation and enhancement of downstream cytokine and chemokine
92 production (Krishnadasan et al., 2003; Pfeffer, 2003). Moreover, these cytokines mediate
93 in the acute phase response (APR) through the regulation of the profile of “positive” or
94 “negative” acute phase proteins (APPs), depending on the increase or decrease of their

95 concentration in serum. Haptoglobin (Hp) and serum amyloid A (SAA), the main positive
96 APPs in cattle, are used as indicators of disease severity (Eckersall, 2000; Petersen et al.,
97 2004). In this sense, various authors have demonstrated that BVDV induces an impaired
98 production of these chemical mediators both *in vitro* and *in vivo*, which could affect to
99 the generation of a subsequent immune response (Adler et al., 1996; Yamane et al., 2005;
100 Lee et al., 2008; Pedrera et al., 2009a; Rivalde et al., 2011).

101 Th1/Th2 paradigm, postulated by Mosmann et al. (1986) from studies on
102 cytokines produced by T lymphocytes in a murine model, is less well defined in
103 ruminants (Estes and Brown, 2002). The functions of Th1 cytokine IFN γ include the
104 stimulation of immunoglobulin production and specific cytotoxicity of T cells, induction
105 of apoptosis and activation of resting tissue macrophages, thereby enhancing resistance
106 against viral infections (Biron and Sen, 2001; Samuel, 2005). This chemical mediator is
107 produced by NK cells, lymphocytes CD8⁺ and CD4⁺ Th1 cells in response to IL-12
108 (Hunter, 2005; Tizard, 2008). On the other hand, the Th2 cytokine IL-4 promotes the
109 development of helper and cytotoxic T cells and the differentiation of immunoglobulins-
110 producing plasma cells from B cells (Tizard, 2008). This cytokine is produced in
111 response to antigen activation by CD4⁺ Th2 cells and some CD8⁺, NK1⁺ and $\gamma\delta$ T cells
112 (Marcenaro et al., 2005). IL-10 is a regulatory cytokine with antiinflammatory effects,
113 inhibiting the activities initiated by proinflammatory cytokines (Biron and Sen, 2001;
114 Pestka et al., 2004). This mediator is produced by all subtypes of Th cells in humans and
115 cattle (Brown et al., 1994, 1998).

116 Previous studies on the immune response set in the Bovine Viral Diarrhea (BVD)
117 do not provide concise results. Whereas some authors demonstrate the establishment of a

118 Th1 response (Charleston et al., 2002; Lee et al., 2008), others maintain that occurs a Th2
119 type immune response which might interfere with protective Th1 responses against other
120 pathogens (Rhodes et al., 1999). However, to our knowledge, no studies have been made
121 on proinflammatory and Th1/Th2 cytokines during co-infections with BVDV and
122 secondary agents in calves.

123 Therefore, the aim of this work was to study the pattern of cytokines implicated in
124 the inflammatory and immune response of calves pre-infected with BVDV and
125 challenged with bovine herpesvirus-1 (BHV-1), as well as evaluate the possible
126 mechanisms used by BVDV to enhance the susceptibility to a secondary infection.

127

128 **Materials and methods**

129 *Animals and experimental design*

130 Thirty male Friesian calves (8-9 months old) were obtained from a herd free of
131 tuberculosis, brucellosis and bovine leucosis virus. The animals were tested to confirm
132 their BVDV and BHV-1 Ags and Abs free status by ELISA.

133 Animals were housed in the Animal Experimental Center of Cordoba University
134 (Spain) and had an adjustment period of one week before the experiment started. The
135 calves were separated in three groups and inoculated as follows:

- 136 - BHV1 group: 12 calves were inoculated with 2 ml (1 ml per nostril) of a suspension
137 of BHV-1.1 Iowa strain with a titration of 10^7 tissue culture infective dose 50%
138 (TCID₅₀)/ml (courtesy of the Hipra Laboratories, Girona, Spain).
- 139 - BVDV/BHV1 group: 14 calves were infected with 10 ml (5 ml per nostril) of ncp
140 BVDV1 strain 7443 containing 10^5 TCID₅₀/ml (courtesy of the Institute für Virologie,

141 TIHO, Hannover, Germany). Twelve days later, when the calves not showed clinical
142 signs and viraemia against BVDV, they were challenged with BHV-1.1.

143 - Negative control group: 4 calves received 1 ml of tissue culture fluid free of virus per
144 nostril.

145 Animals were sedated with xylazine (Rompun® 2% solution; Bayer Healthcare,
146 Kiel, Germany) and euthanatized by overdosing with thiopental-sodium (Thiovet®; Vet
147 Limited, Leyland, Lancashire, UK) in batches of two at 1, 2, 4, 7 and 14 days post-
148 inoculation (dpi) with BHV-1.1. Two animals of the BVDV/BHV1 group were killed
149 before BHV-1.1 inoculation and used as BVDV infection controls in this group. Two
150 animals of the negative control group were euthanatized at the end of the experiment. The
151 entire experimental procedure was carried out in accordance with the Code of Practice for
152 Housing and Care of Animals used in Scientific Procedures, approved by the European
153 Economic Community in 1986 (86/609/EEC amended by the directive 2003/65/EC).

154

155 ***Clinical and pathological examination***

156 Body temperature was recorded and clinical signs were assessed daily during the
157 adjustment period and throughout the study. The clinical evaluation was carried out by a
158 numerical score based on the sum of symptoms like depression, lacrimation, nasal
159 discharge, cough, dyspnoea, nasal lesions and diarrhea valuated individually from 0 to 3,
160 depending on the severity and specificity of the clinical sign.

161 All euthanatized calves were subjected to necropsy examination. Samples were
162 collected from lymphoid tissues, respiratory tract, digestive tract and nervous system,
163 fixed in buffered 10% formalin and embedded in paraffin wax, sectioned and stained with

164 haematoxylin and eosin (HE). Histopathological findings were graded by a numerical
165 score based on the sum of lesions like hyperaemia, petechial haemorrhages, mononuclear
166 infiltrate, lymphoid depletion, apoptosis of lymphocytes and focal necrosis valuated from
167 0 to 3, depending on the severity and specificity of the lesion.

168

169 ***Collected samples***

170 EDTA blood obtained from coccygeal vein and nasal swabs samples were
171 collected at 0, 1, 2, 4, 5, 7, 9 and 14 dpi and frozen at -80 °C until assayed.

172 Blood samples without additive were taken at 0, 3, 6, 9, 12, 15, 18 and 21 hours
173 post-inoculation (hpi), 1, 2, 4, 5, 7, 9 and 14 dpi. Blood was centrifuged at 4000 rpm for
174 10 min and the serum was separated and frozen in aliquots at -80 °C until assayed.

175

176 ***Virological examination***

177 BVDV RNA was extracted from EDTA blood samples using the High Pure Viral
178 Nucleic Acid Kit (Roche, Mannheim, Germany), according to the manufacturer's
179 instructions. A one step Real-Time Reverse Transcription plus Polymerase Chain
180 Reaction (RT-PCR) of the RNA was performed using the primers and Taqman probes (at
181 the same concentration) based on conserved regions of the 5'UTR of BVDV1 described
182 by Letellier and Kerkhofs (2003) and the Real Time Ready RNA Virus Master (Roche,
183 Mannheim, Germany) according to the manufacturer's instructions. The reactions were
184 carried out in a LightCycler 1.5. Any sample that had a cycle threshold (Ct) value less
185 than or equal to 45 was considered as positive. The positive control was the ncp BVDV1
186 strain 7443 at 10^5 TCID₅₀/ml.

187 BHV-1 DNA was extracted from EDTA blood and nasal swabs samples using
188 Genomic DNA Purification kit (Macherey-Nagel, Germany), according to the
189 manufacturer's protocol. The real-time PCR analysis of the extracted DNA template was
190 performed as describes the OIE Terrestrial Manual (OIE, 2010). Data were analyzed on
191 an Applied 7300 detector (Applied Biosystems, USA). Any sample that had a Ct value
192 less than or equal to 45 was considered as positive. The positive control was the BHV-1.1
193 Iowa strain at $10^{8.3}$ TCID₅₀/ml.

194

195 ***Cytokines study***

196 Serum cytokine levels were measured for duplicate by a sandwich ELISA that
197 specifically detects soluble cytokine proteins. IL-1 β , TNF α , IFN γ , IL-12, IL-4 and IL-10
198 protocols make use of commercially available moAbs pairs (Serotec). Briefly,
199 microplates (Nunc Maxisorb, Roskilde, Denmark) were coated with highly purified anti-
200 cytokine Abs at 1 mg/ml in PBS (pH 7.5), except for the bovine IL-1 β (2 mg/ml), and
201 incubated at 4°C overnight. After a blocking step with PBS, 2% Tween-20 and BSA 3%
202 for 1 h at room temperature (Rt) in agitation, the plates were washed 3 times with
203 PBS/Tween-20 and incubated with the serum diluted 1:50 for 1 h at Rt. Then, the plates
204 were washed 3 times and incubated with secondary biotinylated Abs at 1 mg/ml, except
205 IL-1 β (2 mg/ml). This was followed by another washing step and addition of streptavidin-
206 peroxidase (Sigma–Aldrich Química, Spain, 1:1000) for 45 min at Rt. After a final wash,
207 the chromogenic substrate (OPD) was added and absorbance values were measured
208 spectrophotometrically using an ELISA-plate reader (Bio-Rad Laboratories, Spain) at
209 450 nm. Standard curves to calculate cytokine concentrations (ng/ml or pg/ml) were

210 generated using recombinant bovine IL-1 β , TNF α , IFN γ and IL-4 (Serotec). Because of
211 the lack of commercial recombinant bovine IL-10 and IL-12, the results of these
212 cytokines were presented as OD values.

213

214 *APPs analysis*

215 APPs were analyzed for duplicate in serum samples. Hp concentration was
216 measured with a commercial spectrophotometrical assay based on the peroxidase activity
217 of haptoglobin-haemoglobin complexes (Phase Haptoglobin assay, Tridelta). A
218 commercial solid-phase sandwich ELISA was used to determine SAA concentrations
219 (Phase Serum Amyloid A assay, Tridelta). Fibrinogen serum concentration was measured
220 with Biuret method (Total protein Kit, Spinreact SA), calculating the difference between
221 total plasma protein and serum protein. Serum albumin was determined by the
222 bromocresol green method (Albumin Kit, Spinreact SA). All these analysis were
223 performed following the manufacturer's instructions.

224

225 *Serum antibodies detection*

226 The specific detection of BVDV Abs was tested in commercially available
227 competitive ELISA, Ingezim BVD Compac (Ingenasa, Madrid, Spain), following the
228 manufacturer's protocol.

229 Virus neutralization (VN) was applied for the evaluation of Abs response against
230 BHV-1.1 Iowa strain, previously used for secondary infection. Briefly, the test protocol
231 (OIE, 2010) was performed in 96-well microtiter plates with a 24 h virus/serum
232 incubation period and Madin Darby Bovine Kidney cells (MDBK ATCC CCL-22). The

233 plates were incubated for 4 days and the Abs titers were expressed as the reciprocal of the
234 highest dilution that completely neutralized the virus effects in 50% of the wells. Any
235 neutralization at an initial dilution titer of 1 or above was considered as positive.

236

237 ***Statistical analysis***

238 Data were analyzed with the SAS System for Windows, version 9.1 (SAS
239 Institute, Cary, North Carolina, USA). Serum concentration of cytokines and APPs were
240 assessed to calculate mean \pm standard error values. Duncan's Multiple Range Test (P
241 <0.05) was used to analyze significant differences of the values in the same group at
242 various time points (*) and non-paired Student's t-test (P <0.05) was used between both
243 inoculated groups at the same time point (**).

244

245 **Results**

246 ***Assessment of clinical symptoms and post-mortem lesions***

247 The calves in the control group remained clinically unaffected throughout the
248 study. In both inoculated groups, the calves had elevated body temperature and their
249 general appearance was affected in varying degrees. BHV1 group had a slightly affected
250 appearance, showing depression, lacrimation and serous nasal discharge, mainly between
251 7 and 9 dpi. These calves had an elevated rectal temperature (39.6°C) at 5 and 11 dpi.
252 Animals of the BVDV/BHV1 group displayed more severe clinical symptoms, including
253 cough, mucopurulent nasal discharge, dyspnoea, open-mouth breathing, nasal lesions and
254 recurrent diarrhea between 4 and 11 dpi. Moreover, the animals of this group showed
255 more increase of the rectal temperature at 4 and 5 dpi BHV-1.1 ($>40^{\circ}\text{C}$) (Figure 1).

256 There were no remarkable gross or histological lesions in calves of the negative
257 control group. In both inoculated groups, the histological lesions were limited to the
258 digestive tract, respiratory and lymphoid tissues. Digestive lesions were observed in
259 BVDV-inoculated animals which displayed severe depleted lymphoid follicles in the
260 Peyer's patches of the ileum and ileocecal valve throughout the study. In both inoculated
261 groups, the main lesions in the respiratory tract and lymphoid tissues were inflammatory
262 alterations characterized by mononuclear infiltrate composed of Mφs, lymphocytes and
263 plasmatic cells associated with vascular changes. The most severe inflammatory changes
264 were observed in the BVDV/BHV1 group between 4 and 7 dpi (Figure 2).

265

266 ***Virological examination***

267 There was no evidence of any viral infection from blood samples in the animals of
268 the negative control group. BVDV was not detected by RT-PCR in the blood of calves of
269 the BVDV/BHV1 group at the moment of BHV-1.1 inoculation (12 dpi BVDV). The
270 presence of BHV-1.1 antigen was confirmed in both inoculated groups by PCR of nasal
271 swabs samples from 1 dpi onwards, detecting only viraemia in the BVDV/BHV1 group
272 from 4 dpi until the end of the experiment.

273

274 ***Cytokines study***

275 The different analyzed cytokines in the control group maintained low and constant
276 levels without changes in this study (data not showed). The cytokine ELISA results of
277 both inoculated groups are depicted in figures 3 and 4.

278

279 *Proinflammatory cytokines*

280 The proinflammatory cytokines, IL-1 β and TNF α , presented differences in
281 magnitude and kinetics between single and dual infections, mainly from 1 dpi onwards.
282 While the animals of the BHV1 group not showed changes on IL-1 β serum concentration
283 after BHV-1.1 inoculation, the calves of the BVDV/BHV1 group displayed a significant
284 decrease of this cytokine (p=0.03), maintaining low levels until the end of the study
285 (Figure 3). TNF α concentration in the BHV1 group only increased in the later stages, at 9
286 dpi (59 ng/ml; p<0.001), whereas BVDV/BHV1 group showed an earlier and longer
287 response subsequent to BHV-1.1 inoculation. These animals presented a significant
288 increase of this chemical mediator from 1 dpi onwards (p<0.001), peaking at 4 dpi with
289 values 5 times above the baseline level (Figure 3).

290 *Th1/Th2 cytokines*

291 The concentration of Th1 cytokines, IFN γ and IL-12, were elevated in both
292 inoculated groups, although presented differences in magnitude. IFN γ concentration in
293 the BHV1 group displayed an early increase that was maintained with oscillations
294 throughout the study, showing significant values at 5 dpi (4214.62 pg/ml; p<0.0001).
295 However, in the BVDV/BHV1 group, IFN γ serum concentration remained constant from
296 the start of the experiment, peaking only between 4-5 dpi (p<0.0001). There was a similar
297 pattern of IL-12 serum concentration, because the BHV1 group presented a significant
298 increase between 4 and 9 dpi, while the IL-12 levels remained low during the course of
299 the study in the BVDV/BHV1 group, except for an increase at 4 dpi (Figure 4).

300 Th2 cytokine (IL-4) serum concentration not presented changes in any of the
301 studied groups, maintaining low and constant levels throughout the study (Figure 4).

302 Antiinflammatory cytokine (IL-10) concentration displayed a significant increase
303 of twice the baseline level (from 0.18 to 0.45 of OD, approximately) associated with the
304 peak of TNF α in both infected groups, although this increase was longer in BHV1 group
305 (between 7 and 9 dpi) (Figure 4).

306

307 *APPs analysis*

308 APPs serum concentration of the control group remained low and without changes
309 throughout the experiment (data not shown).

310 The serum levels of Hp displayed no significant changes in both inoculated
311 groups in this study. However, SAA protein showed a significant increase in the animals
312 of the BVDV/BHV1 group at 5 and 7 dpi, whereas the calves of the BHV1 group not
313 presented changes in this study. Fibrinogen concentrations followed a similar pattern than
314 SAA protein, showing only the animals of the BVDV/BHV1 group a significant increase
315 at 7 and 9 dpi. Albumin, a negative APP, presented non-significant changes in any group
316 during the experiment (Figure 5).

317

318 *Serum antibodies detection*

319 All animals were negative for BVDV or BHV-1 specific Abs at the start of the
320 study and the uninoculated animals of the control group remained seronegative until the
321 end of the study. Appearance of BVDV-specific serum antibodies were only detected in
322 the calves of the BVDV/BHV1 group from 4 dpi BHV-1.1 (16 dpi BVDV). On the other
323 hand, in both inoculated groups were found neutralizing Abs against BHV-1.1 at 14 dpi,
324 being greater the magnitude in the BVDV/BHV1 group (data not shown).

325

326 Figure 6 depicts a schematic summary of the time-ordered manifestation of
327 clinical signs, virological and immunological parameters addressed in the animals of both
328 BHV1 and BVDV/BHV1 groups.

329

330

Discussion

331 Clinical symptoms and lesions in the BVDV/BHV1 group were more varied and
332 intense than in the BHV1 group; inflammatory processes, in particular, were exacerbated
333 and more widely distributed. This marked inflammatory response in the BVDV/BHV1
334 group was confirmed by analysis of APPs, which showed an increase in SAA protein and
335 fibrinogen, associated with greater secretion of proinflammatory cytokines (TNF α) and
336 reduced production of antiinflammatory cytokines (IL-10) (Petersen et al., 2004;
337 Sánchez-Cordón et al., 2007; Rivalde et al., 2011). The appearance of clinical signs, fever
338 and more intense inflammatory lesions also coincided with a peak in TNF α levels.
339 However, IL-1 β synthesis rather than increasing actually declined, avoiding the
340 appearance of a synergic proinflammatory effect involving TNF α and IL-1 β (Pedrera et
341 al., 2009a; Rivalde et al., 2011). This BVDV-associated inhibition of IL-1 has also been
342 reported *in vitro* coinciding with a lack of TNF α response (Adler et al., 1996; Yamane et
343 al., 2005; Lee et al., 2008), in contrast with our results where TNF α was the main
344 inflammatory mediator. The enhanced inflammatory response observed in the
345 BVDV/BHV1 group highlights the fact that prior inoculation of BVDV does not inhibit
346 the development of a non-specific response to the secondary agent (Gånheim et al.,
347 2003). The results also suggest that the mild inflammatory signs observed in healthy

348 BHV-1-inoculated calves were associated with a transitory increase in TNF α during the
349 final phase of the experiment.

350 Differences in proinflammatory cytokine profiles were accompanied by
351 differences in the synthesis of IL-10, a cytokine with antiinflammatory activity that plays
352 a major role in regulating the immune response (Grutz, 2005). Thus, in the BHV1 group,
353 IL-10 synthesis coincides with that of the proinflammatory cytokines studied, modulating
354 their effect, whereas in the BVDV/BHV1 group the lesions observed suggest that the
355 transitory increase in IL-10 synthesis failed to counteract the action of TNF α .

356 Coinciding with similar findings reported by other authors, both groups of BHV-
357 1-inoculated calves developed a Th1 immune response based on IFN γ production and on
358 the absence of significant changes in IL-4 production over the course of the experiment
359 (Takashima et al., 2002; Abril et al., 2004). However, while the BVDV does not appear
360 to impair the development of a clear Th1 immune response, differences between
361 inoculated groups were apparent with regard to the kinetics and magnitude of IFN γ and
362 IL-12 production, two cytokines that interfere with the spread of BHV-1 by mediating the
363 lysis of infected cells. In the BHV1 group, IFN γ levels rose from the start of the
364 experiment; this increase, together with intense expression of IL-12, could prevent the
365 distribution of BHV-1 from primary replication sites into the blood (Babiuk et al., 1996;
366 Hodgson et al., 2005). In the BVDV/BHV1 group, by contrast, IFN γ did not increase
367 until 4 and 5 dpi, coinciding with the detection of BHV-1 in blood and with mild IL-12
368 production, suggesting an inhibition of the cytotoxic effect on infected cells at the start of
369 the process, associated with the action of BVDV (Lee et al., 2008; Risalde et al., 2011).
370 Moreover, these changes may well be linked to the increase of TNF α in the

394 exacerbation of the inflammatory response and to the development of more intense
395 clinical symptoms and lesions than those observed in healthy animals as a response to a
396 secondary infection. Alterations were also observed in cytokines involved in the
397 cytotoxic mechanisms responsible for limiting the spread of pathogens giving rise to
398 secondary infections, such as BHV-1, thus facilitating the dissemination of this virus. By
399 contrast, prior inoculation of BVDV did not modify the development of a BHV-1-specific
400 humoral response in comparison with that of healthy animals.

401

402 **Conflict of interest statement**

403 None of the authors has any financial or personal relationships that could
404 inappropriately influence or bias the paper.

405

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416

417

References

- 418 Abril, C., Engels, M., Limman, A., Hilbe, M., Albini, S., Franchini, M., Suter, M.,
419 Ackerman, M., 2004. Both viral and host factors contribute to neurovirulence of
420 bovine herpesvirus 1 and 5 in interferon receptor-deficient mice. *J. Virol.* 78,
421 3644-3653.
- 422 Adler, H., Jungi, T.W., Pfister, H., Strasser, M., Sileghem, M., Peterhans, E., 1996.
423 Cytokine regulation by virus infection: bovine viral diarrhoea virus, a flavivirus,
424 downregulates production of tumor necrosis factor alpha in macrophages in vitro.
425 *J. Gen. Virol.* 70, 2650-2653.
- 426 Alvarez, M., Bielsa, J.M., Santos, L., Makoschey, B., 2007. Compatibility of a live
427 infectious bovine rhinotraheitis (IBR) marker vaccine and an inactivated bovine
428 viral diarrhoea virus (BVDV) vaccine. *Vaccine* 25(36), 6613-6617.
- 429 Archambault, D., Beliveau, C., Couture, Y., Carman, S., 2000. Clinical response and
430 immunomodulation following experimental challenge of calves with type 2
431 noncytopathogenic bovine viral diarrhoea virus. *Vet. Res.* 31(2), 215-227.
- 432 Babiuk, L.A., van Drunen Littel-van den Hurk, S., Tikoo, S.K., 1996. Immunology of
433 bovine herpesvirus 1 infection. *Vet. Microb.* 53(1-2), 31-42.
- 434 Biron, C.A., Sen, G.C., 2001. Interferons and other cytokines. In: *Fields of Virology*, 4th
435 Edit., Knipe, D., Howley, P., Griffin, D., Lamb, R., Martin, M., Eds., Lippincott,
436 Williams & Wilkins, Philadelphia, pp. 321-349.
- 437 Brown, W.C., Rice-Ficht, A.C., Estes, D.M., 1998. Bovine type 1 and type 2 responses.
438 *Vet. Immunol. Immunopathol.* 63, 45-55.

439 Brown, W.C., Woods, V.M., Chitko-McKown, C.G., Hash, S.M., Rice-Ficht, A.C., 1994.
440 IL-10 is expressed by bovine type 1 helper, type 2 helper and unrestricted
441 parasite-specific T cell clones, and inhibits proliferation of all three subsets in an
442 accessory cell-dependent manner. *Infect. Immun.* 62, 4697-4708.

443 Charleston, B., Brackenbury, L.S., Carr, B.V., Fray, M.D., Hope, J.C., Howard, C.J.,
444 Morrison, W.I. 2002. Alpha/beta and gamma interferons are induced by infection
445 with noncytopathic bovine viral diarrhoea virus in vivo. *J. Virol.* 76, 923-927.

446 Eckersall, P.D., 2000. Recent advances and future prospects for the use of acute phase
447 proteins as markers of disease in animals. *Rev. Med. Vet.* 151, 577-584.

448 Estes, D.M., Brown, W.C., 2002. Type 1 and type 2 responses in regulation of Ig isotype
449 expression in cattle. *Vet. Immunol. Immunopathol.* 90(1-2), 1-10.

450 Fulton, R.W., Ridpath, J.F., Confer, A.W., Saliki, J.T., Burge, L.J., Payton, M.E., 2003.
451 Bovine viral diarrhoea virus antigenic diversity: impact on disease and
452 vaccination programmes. *Biologicals* 31, 89-95.

453 Gånheim, C., Hultén, C., Carlsson, U., Kindahl, H., Niskanen, R., Waller, K.P., 2003.
454 The acute phase response in calves experimentally infected with bovine viral
455 diarrhoea virus and/or *Mannheimia haemolytica*. *J. Vet. Med. B Infect. Dis. Vet.*
456 *Public. Health.* 50, 183-190.

457 Glew, E.J., Carr, B.V., Brackenbury, L.S., Hope, J.C., Charleston, B., Howard, C.J.,
458 2003. Differential effects of bovine viral diarrhoea virus on monocytes and
459 dendritic cells. *J. Gen. Virol.* 84, 1771-1780.

460 Grutz, G., 2005. New insights into the molecular mechanism of interleukin-10-mediated
461 immunosuppression. *J. Leuk. Biol.* 77, 3-15.

462 Heinz FX, Collet MS, Purcell RH, et al. 2000. Genus pesivirus. In Virus Taxonomy. Eds.
463 Van Regenmortel MHV, Fauquet CM, Bishop DHL, et al., Academic Press,
464 New York, pp. 867-872.

465 Hodgson, P.D., Aich, P., Manuja, A., Hokamp, K., Roche, F., Brinkman, F., Potter, A.,
466 Babiuk, L.A., Griebel, P.J., 2005. Effect of stress on viral-bacterial synergy in
467 bovine respiratory disease: novel mechanisms to regulate inflammation. *Comp.*
468 *Funct. Genom.* 6, 244-250.

469 Hunter, C.A., 2005. New IL-12-family members: IL-23 and IL-27, cytokines with
470 divergent functions. *Nat. Rev. Immunol.* 5, 521-531.

471 Krishnadasan, B., Naidu, B.V., Byrne, K., Fraga, C., Verrier, E.D., Mulligan, M.S., 2003.
472 The role of proinflammatory cytokines in lung ischemia-reperfusion injury. *J.*
473 *Thorac. Cardiovasc. Surg.* 125(2), 261-272.

474 Lee, S.R., Pharr, G.T., Boyd, B.L., Pinchuk, L.M., 2008. Bovine viral diarrhea viruses
475 modulate toll-like receptors, cytokines and co-stimulatory molecules genes
476 expression in bovine peripheral blood monocytes. *Comp. Immunol. Microbiol.*
477 *Infect. Dis.* 31, 403-418.

478 Letellier, C., Kerkhofs, P., 2003. Real-time PCR for simultaneous detection and
479 genotyping of bovine viral diarrhea virus. *J. Virol. Methods.* 114, 21-27

480 Ley, K., Laudanna, C., Cybulsky, M.I., Nourshargh, S., 2007. Getting to the site of
481 inflammation: the leukocyte adhesion cascade updated. *Nat. Rev. Immunol.* 7,
482 678-689.

483 Liebler-Tenorio, E.M., Ridpath, J.E., Neill, J.D., 2004. Distribution of viral antigen and
484 tissue lesions in persistent and acute infection with the homologous strain of
485 noncytopathic bovine viral diarrhea virus. *J. Vet. Diagn. Invest.* 16, 388-396.

486 Liebler-Tenorio, E.M., Ridpath, J.F., Nelly, J.D., 2003. Lesions and tissue distribution of
487 viral antigen in severe acute versus subclinical acute infection with BVDV2.
488 *Biologicals* 31, 119-122.

489 Marcenaro, E., Della Chiesa, M., Bellora, F., Parolini, S., Millo, R., Moretta, L., Moretta,
490 A., 2005. IL-12 or IL-4 prime human NK cells to mediate functionally divergent
491 interactions with dendritic cells or tumors. *J. Immunol.* 174, 3992-3998.

492 Mosmann, T.R., Cherwinski, H., Bond, M.W., Giedlin, M.A., Coffman, R.L., 1986. Two
493 types of murine helper T cell clone. I. Definition according to profiles of
494 lymphokine activities and secreted proteins. *J. Immunol.* 136 (7), 2348-2357.

495 Müller-Doblies, D., Arquint, A., Schaller, P., Heegaard, P.M., Hilbe, M., Albini, S.,
496 Abril, C., Tobler, K., Ehrensperger, F., Peterhans, E., Ackermann, M., Metzler,
497 A., 2004. Innate immune responses of calves during transient infection with a
498 noncytopathic strain of bovine viral diarrhea virus. *Clin. Diagn. Lab. Immunol.*
499 11, 302-312.

500 Murphy, K.M., Reiner, S.L., 2002. The lineage decisions of helper T cells. *Nat. Rev.*
501 *Immunol.* 2, 933-944.

502 Nobiron, I., Thompson, I., Brownlie, J., Collins, M.E., 2001. Cytokine adjuvancy of
503 BVDV DNA vaccine enhances both humoral and cellular immune responses in
504 mice. *Vaccine* 19 (30), 4226-4235.

505 OIE (World organisation for animal health). Infectious bovine rhinotracheitis/ infectious
506 pustular vulvovaginitis. In OIE Terrestrial Manual 2010. Chapter 2.4.13.

507 Pedrera, M., Gómez-Villamandos, J.C., Romero-Trevejo, J.L., Rivalde, M.A., Molina, V.,
508 Sánchez-Cordón, P.J., 2009a. Apoptosis in lymphoid tissues of calves inoculated
509 with non-cytopathic bovine viral diarrhoea virus genotype 1: activation of effector
510 caspase-3 and role of macrophages. *J. Gen. Virol.* 90, 2650-2659.

511 Pedrera, M., Sánchez-Cordón, P.J., Romero-Trevejo, J.L., Rivalde, M.A., Greiser-Wilke,
512 I., Gómez-Villamandos, J.C., 2009b. Morphological changes and viral distribution
513 in the ileum of colostrum-deprived calves inoculated with noncytopathic bovine
514 viral diarrhoea virus genotype-1. *J. Comp. Path.* 141, 52-62.

515 Pestka, S., Krause, C.D., Sarkar, D., Walter, M.R., Shi, Y., Fisher, P.B., 2004. Interleukin-
516 10 and related cytokines and receptors. *Annu. Rev. Immunol.* 22, 929-979.

517 Peterhans, E., Jungi, T.W., Schweizer, M., 2003. BVDV and innate immunity.
518 *Biologicals* 31, 107-112.

519 Petersen, H.H., Nielsen, J.P., Heegaard, P.M., 2004. Application of acute phase protein
520 measurements in veterinary clinical chemistry. *Vet. Res.* 35, 163-187. Review.

521 Pfeffer, K., 2003. Biological functions of tumor necrosis factor cytokines and their
522 receptors. *Cytokine Growth Factor* 14, 185-191.

523 Rescigno, M., Borrow, P., 2001. The host-pathogen interaction: new themes from
524 dendritic cell biology. *Cell* 106, 267-270.

525 Rhodes, S.G., Cocksedge, J.M., Collins, R.A., Morrison, W.I., 1999. Differential
526 cytokine responses of CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ T cells in response to bovine viral
527 diarrhoea virus in cattle. *J. Gen. Virol.* 80, 1673-1679.

528 Ridpath, J.F., Bolin, S.R., Dubovi, E., 1994. Segregation of bovine viral diarrhoea virus
529 into genotypes. *Virology* 205, 66-74.

530 Risalde, M.A., Gómez-Villamandos, J.C., Pedrera, M., Molina, V., Cerón, J.J., Martínez-
531 Subiela, S., Sánchez-Cordón, P.J., 2011. Hepatic immune response in calves
532 during acute subclinical infection with bovine viral diarrhoea virus type 1. *Vet. J.*
533 In press, doi: 10.1016/i.tvil.2011.03.003.

534 Rivera-Rivas, J.J., Kisiela, D., Czuprynski, C.J., 2009. Bovine herpesvirus type 1
535 infection of bovine bronchial epithelial cells increases neutrophil adhesion and
536 activation. *Vet. Immunol. Immunopathol.* 131(3-4), 167-176.

537 Samuel, C.E., 2001. Antiviral action of interferons. *Clin. Microbiol. Rev.* 14, 778-809.

538 Sánchez-Cordón, P.J., Cerón, J.J., Núñez, A., Martínez-Subiela, S., Pedrera, M., Romero-
539 Trevejo, J.L., Garrido, M.R., Gómez-Villamandos, J.C., 2007. Serum
540 concentrations of C-reactive protein, serum amyloid A, and haptoglobin in pigs
541 inoculated with African swine fever or classical swine fever viruses. *Am. J. Vet.*
542 *Res.* 68, 772-777.

543 Schneider-Schaulies, S., Bieback, K., Avota, E., Klagge, I., ter Meulen, V., 2002.
544 Regulation of gene expression in lymphocytes and antigen-presenting cells by
545 measles virus: consequences for immunomodulation. *J. Mol. Med.* 80, 73-85.

546 Takashima, Y., Nagane, N., Hushur, O., Matsumoto, Y., Otsuka, H., 2002. Bovine
547 herpesvirus-1 (BHV-1) recombinant expressing pseudorabies virus (PrV)
548 glycoproteins B and C induces type 1 immune response in BALB/c mice. *J. Vet.*
549 *Med. Sci.* 64(7), 589-596.

550 Tizard, I.R., 2008. Cell signaling: cytokines and their receptors. In: Veterinary
551 Immunology: An Introduction, 8th Edit., IR Tizard, Ed., Elsevier Science,
552 Philadelphia, pp. 70-80.

553 Wilhelmsen, C.L., Bolin, S.R., Ridpath, J.F., Cheville, N.F., Kluge, J.P., 1990.
554 Experimental primary postnatal bovine viral diarrhoea viral infections in six-
555 month-old calves. *Vet. Pathol.* 27(4), 235-243.

556 Yamane, D., Nagai, M., Ogawa, Y., Tohya, Y., Akashi, H., 2005. Enhancement of
557 apoptosis via an extrinsic factor, TNF- α , in cells infected with cytopathic bovine
558 viral diarrhea virus. *Microbes. Infect.* 7, 1482-1491.

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Figure legends

561 **Figure 1.** Rectal temperature ($^{\circ}$ C) and clinical score values of calves inoculated with
562 BHV-1.1 Iowa strain. (0, preinoculation values; h, hour post-inoculation; dpi, days post-
563 infection with BHV-1.1).

564 **Figure 2.** Microscopic lesions score values of calves inoculated with BHV-1.1 Iowa
565 strain. (0, preinoculation values; dpi, days post-infection with BHV-1.1).

566 **Figure 3.** Serum concentrations of the pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-1 β and TNF α) in
567 calves experimentally inoculated with BHV-1.1 versus calves co-infected with BVDV
568 and BHV-1.1. (0, BHV-1.1 pre-inoculation values; h, hour post-inoculation with BHV-
569 1.1; * $p < 0.05$ significant differences in the same group at various time points; ** $p < 0.05$
570 significant differences between groups at the same time point).

571 **Figure 4.** Th1 (IFN γ and IL-12), Th2 (IL-4) and (IL-10) cytokine concentrations in
572 serum of calves inoculated with BHV-1.1 versus calves co-infected with BVDV and

573 BHV-1.1. (0, BHV-1.1 pre-inoculation values; h, hour post-inoculation with BHV-1.1;
574 **p<0.05 significant differences between groups at the same time point).

575 **Figure 5.** Serum concentrations of Hp, SAA, fibrinogen and albumin in calves inoculated
576 with BHV-1.1 versus calves co-infected with BVDV and BHV-1.1. (0, BHV-1.1 pre-
577 inoculation values; **p<0.05 significant differences between groups at the same time
578 point).

579 **Figure 6.** Schematic summary of clinical signs, virological and immunological events
580 occurring in calves infected with BHV-1.1 versus a co-infection with BVDV and BHV-
581 1.1. The length of the bars represents the duration of the parameters studied over the time
582 course of the experiment.

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